

BDAIM-2025

PROCEEDINGS

of the International Scientific and Practical Conference

Big Data and Artificial Intelligence in Modeling
International Socio-Economic Processes

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

May 27, 2025

University of World Economy and Diplomacy
Moscow State Institute of International Relations
National University of Uzbekistan

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Big Data & AI for Global Socio-
Economic Modeling

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in Modeling

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(Conference Proceedings)

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International Scientific and Practical Conference – BDAIM-2025

Big Data and Artificial Intelligence in Modeling International Socio-Economic Processes

The **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**, in collaboration with **MGIMO University** and the **National University of Uzbekistan (NUUz)**, hosted the international scientific and practical conference **BDAIM-2025** on **May 27, 2025** in **Tashkent, Uzbekistan**.

The main **goal** of the conference was to unite researchers, policy makers, experts, and educators to explore cutting-edge applications of **big data** and **artificial intelligence (AI)** in modeling **international socio-economic processes**. Particular emphasis was placed on interdisciplinary approaches and digital transformation in economics, governance, and education.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **Theoretical Foundations:** big data processing, machine learning algorithms, interpretability.
- **Socio-Economic Modeling:** global trade, finance, migration, and digital economies.
- **Global Challenges:** AI for climate change, pandemics, geopolitical risk management.
- **International Relations:** digital diplomacy, media analytics, conflict forecasting.
- **Ethics and Regulation:** AI governance, data protection, algorithmic responsibility.
- **Mathematical Models:** econometrics, game theory, uncertainty and risk analysis.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Neft sanoatining qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalariga integratsiyon tendensiyasi

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Dunyo energetika tizimi hozirgi vaqtda jiddiy o'zgarishlar davrini boshdan kechirmoqda. Iqlim o'zgarishi va global isish bilan bog'liq muammolar, energiyaga bo'lgan talabning o'sishi, shuningdek, atrof-muhitga zarar yetkazadigan omillarning kuchayib borayotgani neft sanoatini o'z strategiyasini qayta ko'rib chiqishga undamoqda. Bugungi kunda ko'plab neft kompaniyalari qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalarini o'z faoliyatiga integratsiya qilish orqali ekologik va iqtisodiy barqarorlikka erishishga intilmoqda. Bunda quyosh, shamol, geotermal, suv va biomassa kabi energiya manbalari asosiy rol o'ynamoqda. Xalqaro Energetika Agentligi (IEA) ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, 2023-yilda qayta tiklanuvchi energiyaning ulushi global energiya ishlab chiqarishda 29% dan ortiqni tashkil etdi. Bu esa neft sanoatining yangi yo'nalishga o'tishini tezlashtirdi. Neft va gaz kompaniyalari tomonidan qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalarini integratsiya qilishiga bir nechta omillar bog'liq. Birinchidan, bularning eng muhim sababi - karbon chiqindilarini kamaytirish va iqlim o'zgarishiga qarshi kurashish zarurati. Shuningdek, qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalarining narxlari ham kamayib borayotgani sababli, ularning integratsiyasi iqtisodiy jihatdan ham maqbul bo'lib qolmoqda.

1-jadval. Quyosh va shamol energiyasi narxlar o'zgarishi

Energiya manbasi	2010-yildagi narx	2020-yildagi narx	narxdagi o'zgarish (%)
Quyosh PV (1 kWh)	0.36 USD	0.07 USD	-80%
Shamol (1 kWh)	0.08-0.14 USD	0.04-0.09 USD	-40%
Offshore Shamol (1 kWh)	0.16 USD	0.07 USD	-50%

*Manba: Integration of Renewable Energy Sources in Oil and Gas Operations a Sustainable Future" by Mohsen

Kiamansouri IntegratingRenewableEnergySolutionsintoOilandGasOperations.

ABusinessCaseforSustainableProfitability.pdf

Masalan, IRENA (Xalqaro Qayta Tiklanuvchi Energiya Agentligi) ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, 2010-yildan beri quyosh fotovoltaiik (PV) texnologiyalarining narxi 80% ga, shamol energiyasining narxi esa 40-50% ga kamaygan. Ushbu o'zgarishlar qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalarini an'anaviy yoqilg'ilar bilan solishtirganda ancha raqobatbardosh qilishga yordam bermoqda. Bu esa neft va gaz kompaniyalarini o'z faoliyatida ushbu texnologiyalarni joriy qilishga undamoqda.

Muvofaqiyatli loyihalar. **Yevropa davlatlari renewable energy loyihalarida** yetakchilik qilmoqda. Masalan, Norvegiyaning Equinor kompaniyasi tomonidan yaratilgan **Hywind Tampen** loyihasi — dunyodagi birinchi suvdagi shamol fermasi bo'lib, Shimoliy dengizdagi neft platformalariga elektr yetkazib bermoqda. Loyiha 88 megavatt (MW) quvvatga ega bo'lib, beshta platformaning yillik elektr ehtiyojining 35 foizini qoplaydi [Equinor, Hywind Tampen Fact Sheet, 2023]. Bu orqali yiliga taxminan 200

ming tonna CO₂ chiqindilarining oldi olinmoqda. Ushbu loyiha garchi 7.4 milliard Norvegiya kroniga (taxminan 700 million AQSh dollari) tushgan bo'lsa-da, uning ekologik va iqtisodiy samarasini hisobga olganda bu sarmoya o'zini oqlamoqda. Yaqin Sharq mamlakatlarida ham bu boradagi ishlar jadallik bilan davom etmoqda. Masalan, Birlashgan Arab Amirliklarida joylashgan **ADNOC** kompaniyasi 2022-yildan boshlab quruqlikdagi barcha neft obyektlarini quyosh va yadroviy energiyaga o'tkazdi [ADNOC, All onshore operations powered by clean energy, 2022]. Shuningdek, u orqali dengiz platformalarini ham HVDC kabellari yordamida toza energiya bilan ta'minlamoqda. Bu orqali kompaniya o'zining dengizdagi operatsiyalaridagi karbon chiqindilarini 30 foizgacha kamaytirishni rejalashtirgan Shimoliy Amerikada ham xususan AQSh va Kanadada, bu jarayon ancha ehtiyotkorlik bilan olib borilmoqda Chevron kompaniyasining Kaliforniyada amalga oshirilgan "**Coalinga Solar-to-Steam**" loyihasi neft sanoatida qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalarining muvaffaqiyatli integratsiya misolidir. Bu loyiha, quyosh energiyasini konsentratsiya qilish orqali ishlab chiqarilgan bug'ni neft qazib olish jarayonida ishlatadi. Natijada, Chevron har yili 31,000 tonnaga yaqin CO₂ gazining chiqindilarini kamaytirishga erishmoqda [11]. Ushbu loyiha Chevronning operatsion xarajatlarini ham pasaytirgan, ya'ni tabiiy gazdan foydalanish o'rniga quyoshdan foydalanish orqali sezilarli darajada iqtisodiy samaradorlikka erishilgan. Bundan tashqari, minglab kichik quyosh tizimlari uzoqdagi nasoslar, SCADA tizimlari va quvurlarni elektr bilan ta'minlab, dizel generatsiyasi xarajatlarini kamaytirmoqda.

2-jadval. Muvaffaqiyatli qayta tiklanadigan energiya loyihalari

Kompaniya	Loyihaning Turli Integratsiyasi	Yutuq	Atrof-muhitga Ta'sir
Chevron	Coalinga Solar-to-Steam Facility	31,000 tonna CO ₂ kamayishi, energiya samaradorligi oshishi	CO ₂ chiqindilarini kamaytirish
Shell	Borssele III/IV Offshore Wind Farm	Yillik 825,000 ta uy uchun energiya ta'minoti	Shamol energiyasidan foydalanish
Norvegiyaning Equinor	Hywind Tampen	Shimoliy dengizdagi neft platformalariga elektr yetkazib bermoqda	200 ming tonna CO ₂ chiqindilarining oldi olinmoqda
ADNOC (BAA)	ADNOC	Neft obyektlarini quyosh va yadro energiyasiga o'tkazdi	Carbon chiqindilarini 30% gacha kamaytirdi

Equinor, Hywind Tampen Fact Sheet, 2023 and ADNOC, All onshore operations powered by clean energy, 2022

Texnologik jihatdan olganda, neft sanoatiga quyidagi qayta tiklanuvchi texnologiyalar faol integratsiya qilinmoqda. **Quyosh PV panellari** – quduqlar, kompressorlar va monitoring tizimlarini elektr bilan ta'minlashda ishlatiladi. Ayniqsa, quyoshli mintaqalarda samaradorligi yuqori.

Quyosh issiqlik texnologiyasi (CSP) – og'ir neftni yerdan chiqarish uchun kerakli bug'ni quyosh orqali ishlab chiqarish. Ummonning Miraah loyihasi buning yaqqol namunasidir (loyiha 600 million dollar atrofida turadi va 80% bug' ta'minlaydi).

Shamol energiyasi – ayniqsa dengiz platformalarida muhim rol o'ynaydi. Misol uchun, Hywind Tampenni aytishimiz mumkin.

Gibrid tizimlar – quyosh, shamol zaxira generatorlar va akkumulyatorlarni birlashtirib, 24/7 elektr uzluksizligini ta'minlaydi.

Energiya saqlash texnologiyalari – batareyalar, gidro saqlash, vodorod ishlab

chiqarish va boshqa usullar yordamida elektr ta'minoti barqarorlashtiriladi. Ammo bu integratsiya jarayoni bir qator muammolarga duch kelinmoqda.

Quyosh va shamol energiyasining o'zgaruvchanligi – bu energiya manbalarining uzluksiz emasligi sababli zaxira tizimlarga ehtiyoj tug'iladi.

Yuqori boshlang'ich xarajatlar – qayta tiklanuvchi loyihalar katta sarmoyani talab qiladi.

Infratuzilmani moslashtirish – mavjud neft obyektlariga yangi texnologiyalarni integratsiya qilish texnik va moliyaviy jihatdan murakkab.

Siyosiy va iqtisodiy noaniqliklar – subsidiyalar, karbon soliqlari va ESG talablaridagi o'zgarishlar kompaniyalarni ehtiyotkorlikka undaydi.

3-jadval. Yevropa Ittifoqi (EU) mamlakatlarining 2017 va 2022 yillaridagi issiqxona gazlari (GHG) chiqindilari bo'yicha ma'lumotlar

EU mamlakatlari	2017-yil GHG chiqindilari (million tonna)	2022-yil GHG chiqindilari (million tonna)	2017-2022 yillardagi o'zgarish (%)
Avstriya	47.6	43.7	-9%
Belgiya	71.6	65.2	-9%
Bolgariya	46.6	43.8	-5%
Xorvatiya	13.7	11.6	-15%
Kipr	5.8	5.8	0%
Chexiya	84.6	76.9	-9%
Daniya	59.3	53.9	-9%
Estoniya	19.1	11.6	-39%
Finlandiya	42.2	33.6	-11%
Fransiya	264.3	253.2	-4%
Germaniya	655.4	542.4	-17%
Gretsiya	56.7	53.8	-5%
Vengriya	39.5	35.7	-10%
Irlandiya	41.7	40.1	-4%
Italiya	261.1	247.7	-5%
Latviya	7.2	6.1	-15%
Litva	10.1	8	-21%
Luksemburg	7.5	7	-7%
Malta	1.5	1.3	-13%
Niderlandiya	151	120.3	-20%
Polsha	300.2	276.4	-8%
Portugaliya	49.6	45.2	-9%
Ruminiya	65.5	54.4	-17%
Slovakiya	11.9	10.1	-15%
Sloveniya	10.6	8.8	-17%
Ispaniya	216.9	181.4	-16%
Shvetsiya	37.4	32.8	-12%
Buyuk Britaniya	480	410	-15%

Manba: Air emissions accounts by NACE Rev. 2 activity Statistics | Eurostat

Jadvalda aksariyat yevropa mamlakatlar uchun 2017-2022 yillarda issiqxona gazlari chiqindilari pasayganligi ko'rsatilgan. O'rtacha pasayish 10% atrofida bo'lib, ba'zi mamlakatlar (Estoniya, Litva, Germaniya, Niderlandiya)da bu pasayish juda sezilarli, 20% dan ortiq. Eng kata pasayish **Estoniya** (39%), **Germaniya** (17%), va **Niderlandiya** (20%) kabi mamlakatlar o'z chiqindilarini sezilarli darajada kamaytirgan. Bu mamlakatlar ekologik transformatsiya va CO2 chiqindilarini kamaytirish uchun jiddiy chora-tadbirlarni amalga oshirgan. Ammo Kiprda esa bu o'zgarish 0% ga teng bo'lgan chunki bu davr mobaynida Kipr hech qanday chora tadbirlar olib bormagan [11]. **Germaniya** va **Buyuk Britaniya** kabi yirik iqtisodiyotlarda chiqindilarning kamayishi sanoat va ishlab chiqarish jarayonlarining yanada ekologik tarzda rivojlanishi bilan bog'liq. Yangi energiya samaradorligi texnologiyalarini tatbiq etish va qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalariga o'tish jarayoni bu pasayishga sabab bo'lgan.

Xulosa qilib aytadigan bo'lsam, neft sanoatining qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalarini integratsiya qilish tendensiyasi global energetika tizimining zamonaviy o'zgarishlariga javob sifatida jadal rivojlanmoqda. Iqlim o'zgarishi va uglerod chiqindilarini kamaytirish ehtiyoji neft kompaniyalarini qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalarini o'z faoliyatlariga integratsiya qilishga undamoqda. Shuningdek, qayta tiklanuvchi energiya texnologiyalarining integratsiyasi nafaqat ekologik barqarorlikni ta'minlash, balki iqtisodiy samaradorlikni oshirishga ham xizmat qilmoqda. Quyosh va shamol energiyasi kabi manbalarning narxlari pasayib borayotgani, ularni integratsiya qilishni yanada qulay qiladi.

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